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Analysis of Bilingual Learning Theories and References (Methods, Techniques, Strategies, Evaluation)

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Abstract

The use of two languages of instruction in bilingual classes, English and Indonesian, in the process of teaching and learning activities is certainly not an easy thing. Teachers must be able to choose the right learning theory and the right and clear learning references, so that the bilingual learning that will be implemented can run well. In the implementation of bilingual learning, there are special designs, plans, or stages that are mature so that the learning process can take place optimally. The design of bilingual learning can be interpreted from various perspectives, such as discussing various studies and theories regarding the strategy and process of learning development and implementation. The result of this study shown that Bilingual learning involves the use of two languages, usually the mother tongue and English, to enhance cognitive abilities, creativity, problem solving and socio-cultural understanding. Bilingual education requires careful planning, with teachers who are proficient in both languages and schools that provide the necessary resources such as teaching materials and infrastructure. Bilingual learning starts with basic vocabulary and simple conversation. The curriculum focuses on real-world words and phrases, which gradually helps students become fluent in both languages, so they can switch from one to the other with ease. Theoretical frameworks, such as the Global English Club approach, support bilingual education through methods such as group discussions and real-world learning experiences. Bilingual learning methods, including the Transition, Maintenance, Enrichment and Legacy approaches, aim to meet students' needs and curriculum objectives. Activities such as role-playing and group discussions further reinforce language retention and active learning in both academic and real-life contexts. Regular evaluation of student progress is necessary for continuous improvement in teaching and learning outcomes.

Keywords: *billangual learning, theory, references*

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INTRODUCTION

The learning process involves interaction between students and teachers during instruction. Improving the quality of learning is expected to improve the overall quality of education. Educators can predict learning outcomes and understand learning theories, and can hypothesize about children's learning steps. In addition, educators can use learning theories and methods, learning concepts and principles to better manage learning. In order to improve the quality of human resources in the field of education, quality schools are needed. A quality school is not only a school that has local excellence through the preparation of educated teachers, but also a school that is able to produce graduates who have the ability to compete internationally.

To produce nationally and internationally recognized graduates, bilingual classes were born. Bilingual learning is an educational approach that uses two languages. The main goal of bilingual learning is to improve students' language intelligence. In bilingual learning, students use a second language in certain subjects such as math, natural science, and foreign language lessons. Students may also be required to use the second language in their daily conversations and communications. The aim is to practice language skills and communication and enrich the vocabulary of the second language.

The use of two languages of instruction in bilingual classes, English and Indonesian, in the process of teaching and learning activities is certainly not an easy thing. Teachers must be able to choose the right learning theory and the right and clear learning references, so that the bilingual learning that will be implemented can run well. In the implementation of bilingual learning, there are

special designs, plans, or stages that are mature so that the learning process can take place optimally. The design of bilingual learning can be interpreted from various perspectives, such as discussing various studies and theories regarding the strategy and process of learning development and implementation.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Meaning of Bilingual Learning

Most schools in Indonesia offer bilingual learning education, also known as bilingual classes, which is a new education system that responds to the challenges of the times and globalization as a whole. Bilingual education is an alternative approach to active foreign language learning that can improve students' cognitive abilities. Bilingual learning is a form of learning that uses two languages simultaneously. In bilingual learning, a combination of the mother tongue and a language other than the mother tongue is usually used. Bilingual learning is learning by using two languages in the implementation of learning. Human resources in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 are required to master science and technology so that bilingual fluency becomes one of the important needs of a person (Lase, 2019). According to Pratiwi (2023), the implementation of bilingual learning requires special and mature design and planning or stages so that the learning process can take place optimally (Pratiwi, n.d.). To implement English or foreign language learning, teachers must have the ability to master both languages, as well as experience and training in organizing foreign language classes. In addition, the school must fulfill all the needs so that the learning process can achieve its goals. However, achieving goals requires many challenges, such as challenges in the implementation of learning. In this case, if there are no adequate resources ranging from teachers to facilities and infrastructure, it will be difficult to achieve optimal results (Nafsiyah, 2018).

In Indonesian primary schools, the concept of bilingual learning is taught to give students basic skills in speaking and understanding two languages. Usually, the learning is contextualized. In Indonesian elementary schools, bilingual learning is taught in the form of vocabulary and conversations that are still in a simple form. In addition, teachers teach vocabulary that students see in the surrounding environment and express it in English, and Indonesian. The vocabulary taught to students is also divided into several categories based on the chapter in the book, such as animals, plants, colors, means of transportation, limbs, and so on. The conversations taught to students are still basic and vary according to grade level, such as: "Good Morning, what is your name? How are you? Where do you live?". The design of bilingual learning can be seen from various perspectives, such as discussing various research theories about strategies and development mechanisms in the implementation of education, creating development standards for various subjects, and creating a system for developing educational quality. Bilingual learning has many benefits from different points of view. From an educational point of view, it helps students to compete in languages, from a cognitive point of view, it enhances creativity, especially in solving problems, and from a socio-cultural point of view it can help them to understand and communicate with people around the world. It is expected that children will be introduced to bilingualism through various non-stressful activities from elementary school age.

The Meaning of Bilingual Learning Theory

Global English Club Bilingual Learning Theory for Elementary School Children

Global English Class evolved to take part in English language learning in elementary schools. Another goal of this learning community is to equip primary school children with the skills to compete in terms of active and passive English skills. Global English Class has developed appropriate bilingual learning strategies so that the theory in the expected level of achievement can be achieved in elementary schools as follows:

- **Biggest Group Discussion**
Learning that is closely related to togetherness to become the learning goal to be achieved is known as Big Group Discussion learning. Familiarizing or approaching children with this group strategy is very important. This system applies the process of learning together with a large number of students, and each group gathers together accompanied by one tutor or learning coordinator at that time.
- **Small Group Learning**
Students in small groups are the same as students in large groups, except that they have a limit on the number of members. This is an important strategy in intensifying mastery. In

the small group system, students are divided into four to five students per group and have one tutor as a learning partner.

- **In Pairs Group Learning**
An educational system theory similar to the two-person learning approach. All children are divided into two groups, and each class group is accompanied by one educator. The concept of learning is very important and must match the child's need for learning. A combination of each with their own advantages.
- **Outing Class Learning**
This system of learning theory uses the process of learning outside the classroom by visiting a place, also known as hands-on learning with nature. The main purpose of this system is that children are encouraged to learn in context by using everything in the learning environment as learning materials.
- **Native Speaker Learning**
Language learning with native language users. the strategy of bringing in guest teachers from abroad. Since English requires the habituation of listening to live English conversations, this serves a very important purpose. In addition, Nativer English accents are more flexible.

Bilingual Learning Methods

In bilingual learning, learners need to master the ability to speak, write, read, and understand communication in classroom learning. Bilingual learning is certainly related to the availability of materials, teachers, media, methods, and evaluations used. A method is a way of achieving something, which means a way to obtain something. Methods in learning are a series of learning models that are systematically arranged and used to achieve learning objectives where students achieve the expected competencies. In bilingual learning, here are the methods that can be used in bilingual learning.

- a. **Transitional**
Transitional bilingual learning usually begins in kindergarten or primary school using the first language as the medium of instruction. Initially, the learner's first language will be used predominantly and gradually reduced and eventually abandoned and replaced by the use of the second language (foreign language). This transitional bilingual learning is done gradually to build or increase their level of bilingualism.
- b. **Maintenance**
Maintenance bilingual learning takes into account the continuous acquisition of the first language even though the second language is used as the language of instruction in the classroom. Maintenance bilingual learning does not involve the development or expansion of the second language used. The use of second language skills is also not completed in advance as they will be used to master the subject area at the next level.
- c. **Enrichment**
Enrichment bilingual learning is bilingual learning that considers both languages equally important in learning. This enrichment bilingual learning does not just achieve an understanding of linguistic factors but rather an understanding and skill in the use of the communicative function of the language.
- d. **Heritage**
This bilingual learning is a combination of several bilingual learning with the aim of passing on foreign languages to prevent extinction. Learners in this bilingual learning have a greater understanding of foreign languages so that they can communicate well in this learning.

From previous research that has been obtained, a study by Fera Setyowati (2020) on bilingual learning at MI Muhammadiyah Ajibarang Kulon Banyumas shows that learning in class 2 uses the PPP method (Presentation, Practice, and Production). Presentation is an activity where the teacher presents and explains the material to students, then practice or practice carried out by students such as practicing dialogue or conversation, then there is production or production in the sense that students produce by looking for topics related to the material that has been taught then making a product as creative as their ideas without being guided by the teacher. In addition, students are also invited to play roleplay if there is material about dialogue and stories.

Another previous research conducted by Siti Muawanah at SDIT Al Ikhlas Bekasi in 2023 showed that at SDIT Al Ikhlas Bekasi there is also bilingual learning in the classroom which is carried out every day using the habituation method in daily activities and in every activity held by the school. Learners are given a stimulus by always speaking English in activities. Learners are invited by teachers to communicate using English even with teachers who do not teach English. Learners communicate with English both in the school environment and outside the school environment. Bilingual learning at SDIT Al Ikhlas Bekasi is also implemented with the greeting morning program and daily vocab.

Bilingual Learning Techniques

Techniques are ways in which one implements a method. So to implement bilingual learning methods, the following techniques are needed.

- a. Identifying the characters, behaviors and learning styles of the learners to determine the suitable learning
- b. Choosing a learning approach system based on the qualifications of the learners
- c. Determining suitable steps, methods, models and strategies to be used in learning
- d. Establish rules and limits of success or criteria that can be used as benchmarks or guidelines in evaluating the results of learning activities so that future learning will be better.

Bilingual class implementation strategy

The implementation of bilingual classes has started since 2023 and even schools outside big cities have also implemented bilingual classes. This is because the application of bilingual classroom learning can be considered to bring benefits to students, such as increasing student creativity, increasing cognitive intelligence, and making it easier for students to adapt to various conditions. There are five strategies for implementing bilingual classes, which are as follows:

1. Able to speak foreign languages, such as English very well. It is expected that students can communicate with the teacher during the learning process. Which is expected so that learning can run well.
2. Using videos to teach, using learning videos can improve students' understanding of the subject when applying bilingual learning methods easily. This is because it is easier for students to understand the subject matter delivered through videos. At this time teachers can make videos of the subject matter for students.
3. Watching movies, by watching movies can improve students' foreign language skills and make students able to think creatively, students are encouraged to choose movies such as cartoons such as the lion king movie, and hero movies, etc. However, it is important to choose movies that are watched by students. However, the movie watched with students is a movie that is intended for all ages and does not have scenes of violence.
4. Require students to ask questions, add opinions, answer questions, and give opinions, to improve students' foreign language (English) skills, so that it can facilitate teachers in implementing bilingual learning methods. Teachers should occasionally ask students to explain the subject matter that has just been taught. In order to encourage students to give their opinions, the teacher can also give a small appreciation for students who have the courage to express their opinions. For example, by giving star stickers or chocolates. However, if there is a student's grammar or grammar that is not correct, do not immediately scold the student. This can actually reduce self-confidence and make students reluctant to use foreign languages.

Participating in training, to improve foreign language skills, teachers can now easily improve foreign language skills by participating in training on digital platforms, teachers can take part in online training using gadgets (such as cellphones, tablets, or laptops). In addition, teachers can also determine when is the most appropriate time to take the training. So, the teacher's work to teach is not interrupted.

Evaluation of Bilingual Learning

Learning evaluation is defined as determining the suitability between student performance and learning objectives. In this case, what is evaluated are student characteristics using a certain benchmark. These characteristics in the scope of teaching and learning activities are student displays in the cognitive (knowledge and intellectual), affective (attitudes, interests, and motivation), and psychomotor (skills, movements, and actions) fields.

These displays can be evaluated orally, in writing, or in action. Thus, evaluating here is determining whether the student's display is in accordance with the instructional objectives that have been formulated or not.

Evaluation of a program is carried out with the aim of being able to see and observe the success of the program. The results of the evaluation can later be used as a reference in developing the implementation and implementation of the program.

Evaluation is carried out based on student learning outcomes, the learning outcomes in question are in the form of daily assignment grades which are carried out four times a semester, semester exam grades or mid-semester assessments (PTS), and final exam grades or end-of-semester assessments (PAS).

CONCLUSION

Bilingual learning involves the use of two languages, usually the mother tongue and English, to enhance cognitive abilities, creativity, problem solving and socio-cultural understanding. Bilingual education requires careful planning, with teachers who are proficient in both languages and schools that provide the necessary resources such as teaching materials and infrastructure. Bilingual learning starts with basic vocabulary and simple conversation. The curriculum focuses on real-world words and phrases, which gradually helps students become fluent in both languages, so they can switch from one to the other with ease. Theoretical frameworks, such as the Global English Club approach, support bilingual education through methods such as group discussions and real-world learning experiences. Bilingual learning methods, including the Transition, Maintenance, Enrichment and Legacy approaches, aim to meet students' needs and curriculum objectives. Activities such as role-playing and group discussions further reinforce language retention and active learning in both academic and real-life contexts. Regular evaluation of student progress is necessary for continuous improvement in teaching and learning outcomes.

SUGGESTIONS

Elementary school teacher education students, as prospective teachers, must understand relevant and appropriate learning theories and references to be implemented in bilingual education to improve their competence and become professional educators.

REFERENCES

- Alindra, A. L., Kholillah, K., Khomsanua, A., Nurfitriana, R., Fatikhah, T., & Citra, W. R. (2024). Penerapan Kelas Bilingual terhadap Peningkatan Mutu Belajar di Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Pendidikan Tambusai*, 8(1), 1685-1696.
- Effendi, A. M., Rini, S., & Kusumawati, E. R. (2022). BILINGUAL LEARNING IN GLOBAL ENGLISH CLASS LEARNING COMMUNITIES FOR ELEMENTARY SCHOOL LEVEL CHILDREN. *Maharot: Journal of Islamic Education*, 6(2).
- Elis Ratna Wulan, E., & Rusdiana, A. (2015). Evaluasi pembelajaran.
- Khauzanah, A. N., Budiman, M. A., Wakhyudin, H. (2023). MANAJEMEN PROGRAM BILINGUAL BERBASIS PENDIDIKAN HOLISTIK DI SD HJ. ISRIATI BAITURRAHMAN 2 SEMARANG. *Wawasan Pendidikan*, 3(2).
- Lase, D. (2019). Pendidikan di Era Revolusi Industri 4.0. *SUNDERMANN: Jurnal Ilmiah Teologi, Pendidikan, Sains, Humaniora dan Kebudayaan*, 12(2), 28–43.
- Muawanah, S. (2023). Manajemen Program Sekolah Bilingual Tingkat Sekolah Dasar Islam. *Tawazun: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam*, 16(3), 645-656.
- Setyowati Fera. (2020). Model Pembelajaran Bilingual di MI Muhammadiyah Ajibarang Kulon Kecamatan Ajibarang Kabupaten Banyumas. Skripsi, Fakultas Tarbiyah Dan Ilmu Keguruan, Institut Agama Islam Negeri Purwokerto.
- Uma, L. M. W., Beku, V. Y., & Noge, M. D. (2024). Analisis Penerapan Pembelajaran Bilingual Siswa Kelas IV SDI Rutosoro. *Jurnal Terapi Wicara dan Bahasa*, 2(2), 917-936.